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Research Article

**SOCIO-ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS OF POULTRY EGG
FARMERS IN BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN: A PERCEPTIONAL
ANALYSIS****Muhammad Asif Musakhail¹, Dr. Ahmed Ali Mengal^{1*}, Dr. M. A. Tareen²,
Muhammad Ayub Babar¹**¹Agriculture Research Institute Agriculture Research (ARI) Sariab Quetta Balochistan, Pakistan.²Department of Agricultural Extension, Agriculture and Cooperatives Department Quetta
Balochistan, Pakistan.**Abstract:**

Present text aim was to explore the perceived perceptions paradigm of the respondents regarding the socio-economic determinants in the purposively districts (Mastung, Pishin and Loralai) in Balochistan province. A descriptive type of research design was used in the present research. Sample size of sixty (60) farmers (poultry egg farmers) 20 from each district were selected through the simple random sampling method. Data was analyzed by using the SPSS. Results reveal that half (50%) of the poultry egg farmers were uneducated. Most (41.66%) of the poultry egg farmers having farming experiences possession as 11-20 years. Most (46.66%) of the poultry egg farmers perceived that their family size were consisted the 10-16 members. Most (46.66%) of the poultry egg farmers were preferred the combine and joint family system. More than half (51.66%) of the poultry egg farmers were satisfied the rearing of birds in good hygienic condition. Therefore, In this regard, livestock department and research institutes should promoted the joint-venture programs and given due attention to the promotion of egg production as part of the research development programs for the small and marginal famers so as to eliminate the poverty and promote the income generation process for the underprivileged communities.

Key words: socio-economic, poultry, Balochistan, determinants.**Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

OVERVIEW: Pakistan is the fast growing agricultural country having growth rate 2.2% annually with total population of 182,589,000 people, which represents an increase of 3,428,889 people compared to 2012. Most of peoples are engaged in agriculture producing food for her nation. The food is derived from agricultural products such as vegetable and animal products. Animal products are the traditional sources of milk, meat and eggs consumed by people since pre-historic times. They provide not only the essential amino acids but also the minerals, fats and vitamins. Among animal products, the egg is the most consumable item in the families especially in the children. Chicken eggs are a most common food and one of the most cooking items contains 65, 35, 12, 11, 1 and 11% water, dry matter, protein, fat, carbohydrates and ash respectively. The chicken egg also contains 163 cal/100g. The boiled and omelet are the major food item used in diets regularly. The egg acts as a nutritional powerhouse and can help the body to prevent as well as get rid of different ailments. Eating a raw egg is similar to consuming a good health tonic, whereas having boiled eggs is equally beneficent. The breakfast time is the best time to consume eggs daily. There are many benefits of egg including maintains health, provides nutrition and protects immune system. In Pakistan, 13425 million numbers of eggs are produced for the consumption [1].

Poultry in Pakistan was kept as backyard business for household needs. In early sixties the need of commercial poultry was felt which resulted in 1963, in the form of a national campaign to enhance the production of feed products in the country. Under this campaign the government announces a tax exemption policy on the income derived from poultry farming. Pakistan International Airlines (PIA) in collaboration with Shaver Poultry Breeding Farms of Canada started first commercial hatchery in Karachi. Simultaneously, a commercial poultry feed mill was started by Lever Brothers (Pvt), Pakistan Ltd., at Rahim Yar Khan, which was followed by other pioneers like Arbor Acres Ltd. Special emphasis was laid by the Government on development of poultry industry in the country during 1965-75. The Government made major policy decisions to provide all possible facilities to poultry industry in the annual development plans. In this period was a disaster due to diseases, in 1990 the farmers suffered a great loss due to Hydro pericardium syndrome specially the farmers of Broiler and Broiler Breeder Birds.

In 1991-92 another disease Gumboro attacked the chicks of broiler, layer and parent flock that resulted

in great mortality. With the passage of time efforts to reduce the incidence of these diseases and prophylaxes regarding vaccination and bio-security were done, this also resulted in establishment of new medicine companies and the importation of vaccines form abroad started. At national level institutes like Poultry Research Institute, Veterinary Research Institute and Agriculture University Faisalabad also done efforts to reduce these diseases. In 1995 a new disease Avian Influenza appeared in Murree and Abbotabad and mortality in parent flock rose up to 80% due to this disease and set a challenge to the scientists at national level. Conferences at the diagnosis of this disease were conducted in which scientists discussed their point of views, after great loss measures were adopted that resulted in controlling the disease [2].

In 1996 parent flock increased in number due to absence of planning that resulted in depression in the market and the price of chicks decreased several times its cost of production. This depression in Poultry market continued in 1997 as result of ban on serving of lunch in marriage parties that reduced the demand of poultry products in the market up to 40%. Slowly in 1998 it started improving and by increase in price of chick the companies got a great profit. 1999 again a syndrome like influenza broke that cause great losses in some areas while some areas were safe. Now still there are many threats to the poultry industry the manor of which is the marketing problems of chicks to finished products, a great planning is required in this regard. At this time it is supposed that big firms like be Jan can be help full to reduce the instability of the market but it may be before time [3].

Balochistan province has considered deprived portion of the country. Agriculture and livestock sectors were bulky contributors of the province economy [4]. Both sectors rendered their agricultural extension services but unfortunately the fruits of these effort have not been benefited as yet so for [5]. Therefore, keeping in the view statement above present efforts has been carried out regarding the socio-economic determinants regarding the poultry egg production in Quetta district Balochistan, Pakistan.

Objectives

1. To study the socio-economic characteristics of the poultry egg farmers in the study area.
2. To explore the perceived perception of egg

producers regarding the hygiene practices.

- To developed the need-based recommendations for improvement of the poultry and egg productivity at national level for policy-makers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Research Design

A descriptive type of research design was used in the present research.

Study Area

Face-to-face interaction as the interview methods was used in the present research. The information was gathered by using the field survey of sixty (60) farmers (producers of poultry) as the simple size in the study areas.

Target population

A sample size of sixty (60) farmers (producers of poultry/egg) were selected through the simple random sampling method from Mastung district (20), Pishin district (20) and Loralai (20) =60.

Questionnaire development

Keeping in the view objectives of the current research, a comprehensive questionnaire was administrated so as to detect the perceived perception of the respondents on diverse constructs.

Socio-economic Characteristics

The status of the sample respondents can be well described through socio-economic characteristics. In this study, different indicators of respondent's socio-economic features were identified as independent variables.

Data Collection

The primary data was gathered at field level. The respondents were perceived to provide their perceptions regarding the poultry eggs farming in purposively selected districts.

Data Analysis

Collected data was contained by nature as quantitative information. First the information's as was installed into the tally sheet in the Microsoft Office Excel software. Afterwards, the data put into SPSS 17 package for data analysis.

RESULTS:

Socio-Economic Characteristics

Age of farmers

Farmer's age is considered imperative demographic factor that influences the decision-making process. In this regard, the age as the independents variables was categorized into four stages as shown in figure-2.

Figure 1: Socio-economic attribution regarding age

The age composition of the respondents (poultry egg farmers) were asked. Most (31.66%) of the poultry egg farmers were fall in age group of 31-40 years as perceived by the 19 poultry egg farmers. While most 30% of the poultry egg farmers were fall in age group of (41 to 50) years. Only 18.33% of the poultry egg farmers were fall in age group of 81-30 years. It was further mention that the aged poultry egg farmers have more experiences as compare to who have less experience regarding the rearing and maintaining the poultry.

Education level of farmers

Education foci theme as stressed towards the desirable changes in human attitude in dynamic ways. In this connection the raw information was collected as shown in figure-2. In its general sense is a form of learning in which the knowledge, skills, and habits. The education system in Pakistan is generally divided into five levels: primary (grades one through five); middle (grades six through eight); high (grades nine and ten, leading to the Secondary School Certificate or SSC); intermediate (grades eleven and twelve, leading to a Higher Secondary (School) Certificate or HSC); and university programs leading to undergraduate and graduate degrees.

Figure 2: Socio-economic attribution regarding education level

Half (50%) of the poultry egg farmers were uneducated, followed by 43% of the poultry egg farmers were matriculation. Only (13.33%) of the poultry egg farmers reach at primary level, and 1.66% bachelor/master education in the study area.

Farming experience of farmers

Poultry farm experience mean, which includes monitoring the welfare of the birds, feeding them and ensuring fresh drinking water is always available.

Figure 3: Socio-economic attribution regarding farming experience

The results of figure-3 shows that most (41.66%) of the poultry egg farmers having farming experiences possession as 11-20 years. While 25% of the poultry egg farmers having poultry farming experience above 30 years. Only 13.33% of the poultry eggs farmers had experience up to 10 years.

Family size of farmers

Family is a social group in society typically consisting of parents and their children’s. Two or more people who share goals and values, have long-term commitments to one another, and reside usually in the same dwelling place.

Figure 4: Socio-economic attribution regarding family

The poultry egg farmers were inquired to show their perceptions regarding family size as shown in figure-4 shows. Most (46.66%) of the poultry egg farmers perceived that their family size were consisted the 10-16 members. Only 38.33% of the poultry egg farmers professed that their family unit size were consisted the 2 to 9 members.

Family Type of farmers

Joint family set-up, the workload is shared among the members, often unequally. The roles of women are often restricted to housewives and this usually involves cooking, cleaning, and organizing for the entire family. Extended family defines a family that extends beyond the nuclear family, consisting of grandparents, aunts, uncles, and cousins all living nearby or in the same household. A single-family detached home, also called a single-detached dwelling or separate house is a free-standing residential building

Figure 5: Socio-economic attribution regarding family type

The results of figure-5 shows that most (46.66%) of the poultry egg farmers were preferred the combine and joint family system. While (43.33%) of the poultry egg farmers were chosen the single family type.

Hygienic

Hygiene is a set of practices performed for the preservation of health. While in modern medical sciences there is a set of standards of hygiene recommended for different situations.

Figure 6: Socio-economic attribution regarding hygienic

The hygienic conditions were categorized into three segments. In this regard, the results of figure-6 reveals that, more than half (51.66%) of the poultry egg farmers were satisfied the rearing of birds in good hygienic condition. While 35% of the poultry egg farmers did not agreed with the statement regarding the hygienic condition of birds were poor.

DISCUSSION:

The perceived perceptions of the poultry egg farmers were detected regarding the socio-economic determinants and attitudinal aspects. Similar, present research was also identified the perceptual directions, factors and believed that would be influential the decision-making of the poultry egg farmers in the purposively selected districts (i.e. Mastung, Pishin and Loralai) of, Balochistan, Pakistan. However, in this regard,

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

For the promotion of poultry egg following strategy should be adopted.

Socio-economic dominants are considered as the imperative aspects of the current study. In this regard, socio-economic conditions within term of age, educational status, marital status, gender and farming experiences have reflects the positive impact over on decision-making process. In this context, for instance, a farmers who having the high qualification status and experienced age composition, the adoptability

rate of those farmers higher than those who have Illiterate or uneducated or less experiences. In this regard, livestock department and research institutes should promoted the joint-venture programs and given due attention to the promotion of egg production as part of the research development programs for the small and marginal famers so as to eliminate the poverty and promote the income generation process for the underprivileged communities. There is need of proper guide to farmers about egg production should be delivered by public sectors (livestock and extension department) so that enable to famers to obtained the desirable income for their poultry production.

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